

SECURITY IN CRISIS SITUATIONS IN THE BORDER REGIONS OF POLAND AND UKRAINE

Scientific Papers of the International Scientific Conference

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Edited by:

Leszek Buller

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Rare biodiversity of highland ecosystems as an indicator of the sustainability of the Chornohora Massif in the Ukrainian Carpathians

Roman Cherepanyn PhD, Ass. Prof.,

Nadiya Riznychuk PhD, Ass. Prof.,

Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University in Ivano-Frankivsk,
Department of Biology and Ecology, Faculty of Natural Sciences

Abstract

The rare biodiversity of highland ecosystems of the Ukrainian Carpathians is analyzed in the article. The peculiarities of the highland nature and the main research activities conducted in the region are described. Information on the distribution and ecology of some rare species and their nature conservation status is provided. The importance of rare biodiversity at different organization levels – from populations to ecosystems – for maintaining the sustainability of the Chornohora massif and the Carpathians is explained. Approaches of rare species, natural communities, and habitat conservation in different natural environment conditions and anthropogenic influences are suggested.

Keywords: rare species of plants, highland ecosystems, Chornohora massif, Ukrainian Carpathians, nature conservation, sustainable development.

Under the Framework Convention on the Protection and Sustainable Development of the Carpathians, which was ratified by seven countries of Central and Eastern Europe, including Ukraine, biodiversity plays one of the leading roles in ensuring the sustainable development and security of the Carpathian region¹. The diversity of wildlife is an indicator of the stability of social and environmental systems, ensures functional connections between natural communities, and maintains biogeochemical processes in the biosphere at the appropriate level. Biodiversity is studied at different levels, the main of which are population, species, and ecosystem. Nowadays, the processes of species disappearance and degradation of ecosystems have acquired a massive character. Therefore, biodiversity conservation constitutes one of the key tasks of modern times².

The change in the natural conditions and anthropogenic activity in the Ukrainian Carpathians has led to a decrease in habitats and the changing functional organization of many species. Most of them are rare, endemic or boundary area species. They are mainly represented by isolated

1 Закон України від 07.04.2004 № 1672-IV «Про ратифікацію Рамкової конвенції про охорону та сталий розвиток Карпат» [https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/go/001_001-17 – доступ від 20.10.2022].

2 WWF. Living Planet Report 2016. Risk and resilience in a new era / [H. Strand, A. Winkelhagen, M. Barrett, M. Grooten]; editor-in-Chief: N. Oerlemans. – WWF International, Gland, Switzerland. – 2016. – 144 pp.

populations which differ in their genetic and ecological structure and are confined to certain types of habitats that are separated from each other by geographical or biological barriers³. Researchers who study biodiversity take the population level as the basic one since the population is an element of ecosystems, micro-evolutionary processes take place in it, and it is the unit of conservation of species and natural communities⁴.

The rare species of highland ecosystems of the Ukrainian Carpathians, in particular the Chornohora massif, play an important indicative role in assessing the sustainability of natural systems in the region. In the Ukrainian Carpathians, among rare species, there is a significant part of cenosis-forming species. A specific group consists of endemic and arctic-alpine species – the last are relicts from previous geological epochs and glacial ages.

Rare species can play the role of model organisms in studies on ecosystem responses to climate change, which is particularly relevant today. The useful and aesthetic properties of many of them have led to their active use by humans. This has resulted in a decrease in the distribution area, changes in the population structure, and other negative processes.

In the Ukrainian Carpathians, many rare species are confined to glacial forms of relief – ancient glacial cirques and rocky ridges of mountain ranges. There are not so many geographical massifs in the region that would be characterized by a similar landscape. In particular, the Chornohora, Svydovets, Maramures, and Chyvchyny Mountain Massifs serve as a refugium for rare arctic-alpine species. They also appear in other territories, but the mentioned above areas are the centers of their distribution in the Ukrainian Carpathians.

According to the provisions of the Berne Convention⁵ and the Habitats Directive⁶, the protection of the natural environment of species and the provision of conditions for their reproduction is one of the important mechanisms of biodiversity conservation. That is why protecting highland habitats and ecosystems is the primary task in the rare species conservation of the Chornohora massif and the Ukrainian Carpathians.

The Ukrainian Carpathians are a part of the Eastern Carpathians within the territory of Ukraine. Their width is about 100 km, and their length reaches 280 km. The total area is about 2400 square kilometres⁷. Mountain chains stretch from the northwest to the southeast. The relief of the mountains is characterized by asymmetry – the northeastern slopes of the ranges are steeper compared to the southwestern ones. This is caused by the specifics of the geological structure and the influence of the Pleistocene glaciation. The northern slopes are often represented by steep glacial cirque walls with rock outcrops that create deep depressions.

3 Структура популяцій рідкісний видів флори Карпат / За ред. К. Малиновського. – Київ: Наук. думка, 1998. – 173 с.

4 Грант В. Видообразование у растений / В. Грант. – М.: Мир, 1984. – 528 с.

5 Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats. – 1979, E. T. S. 104; IEL-MT 979: 70.

6 Ibid.

7 Природа Українських Карпат: [зб. наук. праць / наук. ред. Геренчук К. І.]. – Львів: Вид-во Львів. ун-ту, 1968. – 267 с.

The southern slopes, which were less affected by glaciers, are declivous and covered with meadow grass vegetation.

Chornohora, Svydovets, and Maramures massifs are the main highland areas of the Ukrainian Carpathians. They are characterized by the presence of the most typical alpine landscapes with sharp peaks, rock outcrops, and large ranges of amplitudes⁸.

The Chornohora highlands begin from the Chorna Tysa River with Mount Sheshul, behind which there stretches the highest massif chain of peaks of the Ukrainian Carpathians: Petros, Hoverla, Breskul, Pozhyzhevska, Dancer, Turkul, Rebra, Gutyn-Tomnatyk, Brebeneskul, Munchel, Dzembronya, Pip-Ivan. The length of the highland part of the Chornohora Range is about 35 km, the width is more than 3 km, and the average height is about 1,750 m⁹. Several spurs branch off from the main range in the northeastern direction: the Shpytsi, Kedruvatyi Pohorilets, Rozshybenyk ranges, and Mount Smotrych. There are three large and about two dozen of small alpine lakes of glacial origin within the Chornohora massif – Nesamovyte, Brebeneskul, Maricheyka, etc.

The nature of the Ukrainian Eastern Carpathians has been a subject of interest for scientists since the middle of the 19th century. In particular, the vegetation of the Pokuttya-Maramures region was analyzed during that period by the famous Polish botanist and traveller Hugo Zapałowicz¹⁰. Researchers of the first half of the 20th century also worked actively in these and related areas. The vegetation of Svydovets was studied by the Czechoslovak botanist and politician Karel Domin¹¹; the flora, climate and soils of Pip-Ivan of Maramures were studied by Miloš Deyl¹²; highland peatlands of Chornohora – by Hryhoriy Kozij¹³; Andrzej Środoń¹⁴ worked on the dynamics of the forest line upper limit on Chornohora and the Chyvchyny Mountains; the publications of Polish scientists Bogumil Pawłowski¹⁵ and Jan Walias¹⁶ are dedicated to the vascular plants of the Chyvchyny Mountains. Already at the beginning of the 20th century, scientists

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- 8 Малиновський К. А. Рослинність високогір'я Українських Карпат / К. А. Малиновський. – К.: Наук. думка, 1980. – 280 с.
 - 9 Romer E. Próba morfometrycznej analizy grzbietów Karpat Wschodnich / E. Romer // Kosmos. – 1909. – 34. – S. 678–693.
 - 10 Zapałowicz H. Roślinna szata gór Pokucko-Marmaroskich / H. Zapałowicz // Spraw. kom. fizjograf. Kraków. – 1889. – T. 24. – 389 s.
 - 11 Domin K. Šimanův kotel na Svidovci v Podkarpatské Rusi / K. Domin // Věstn. Král. Čes. spol. nauk. Mat.-přírod. – 1930. – Tř. 2. – S. 1–20.
 - 12 Deyl M. Plants, soil and climate of Pop Ivan: Synecological Study from Carpathian Ukraina / M. Deyl // Opera Botan. Čechica, 2. J. Šefl Press, Praha. – 1940. – 290 pp.
 - 13 Kozij G. Wysokogórskie torfowiska północno-zachodniego pasma Czarnohory / G. Kozij // Pam. Państw. Inst. nauk. gosp. wiejsk. w Puławach. – 1932. – 13. – S. 163–179.
 - 14 Środoń A. Górna granica lasu na Czarnohorze i w Górach Czywczyńskich / A. Środoń // Pol. Akad. Umiejętn. – 1948. – T. 72. – 92 s.
 - 15 Pawłowski B. Zagadnienie ochrony szaty roślinnej Gór Czywczyńskich / B. Pawłowski // Ochr. Przyr. – 1937. – R. 17. – S. 93–110.
 - 16 Pawłowski B. Les associations des plantes vasculaires des Monts de Czywczyn / B. Pawłowski, J. Walas // Bull. Acad. Pol. Scient. et Lettr. Ser. B. – 1949. – P. 117–181.

understood the importance and uniqueness of the Eastern Carpathians, in particular the nature of the Chornohora massif, as evidenced by the conservation justification of the Chornohora Reserve and the research conducted by Stanisław Kulczyński, Oleksandr Kozikovskiy and the famous Lviv botanist Tadeusz Wilczyński¹⁷.

In the middle of the 20th century, due to the active development of the highland nature, the studies of secondary phytocenosis (mostly *Nardus stricta* L. and shrub communities) began, and they continue developing at present time¹⁸. In the subalpine zone, the peculiarities of the functioning of a number of dominant and assectator species in the communities of *Festuca rubra* L.¹⁹, *Rumex alpinus* L.²⁰, *Vaccinium myrtillus* L.²¹ and *Pinus mugo* Turra²² were analyzed. Much attention was paid to the reproduction of highland species in the works of I.V. Vaynagiy²³. The biology and ecology of widely distributed species were studied: *Homogyne alpina* (L.) Cass., *Soldanella hungarica* Simonk., species of *Petasites* genus (*Petasites* Mill.)^{24, 25}.

A significant contribution to the study of the populations of rare, endemic, relict, and boundary area species was made by the School of Population Ecology of the Institute of Ecology of the Carpathians of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (K.A. Malynovsky, Y.V. Tsaryk, H.G. Zhyliayev, V.G. Kyvak, Y.Y. Kobiv, V.M. Bilonoha, R.I. Dmytrakh, I.M. Danylyk, N. M. Sychak,

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- 17 Kulczyński S. / Czarnohora jako rezerwat przyrodniczy / S. Kulczyński, A. Kozikowski, T. Wilczyński // Ochrona przyrody. – 1926. – N 6. – S. 23–34.
 - 18 Малиновський А. К. Монтанный элемент флоры Украинских Карпат / А. К. Малиновський // Отв. ред. Ю. Р. Шеляг-Сосонко. – К.: Наук. думка, 1991. – 240 с.
 - 19 Дмитрах Р. И. Экология опыления компонентов сообщества овсяницы красной в Карпатах: автореф. дисс. на соискание науч. степени канд. биол. наук: спец. 03.00.05 “Ботаника” / Дмитрах Р. И. – Днепропетровск, 1991. – 16 с.
 - 20 Кобив Ю. И. Структурно-функциональная организация щавельников Украинских Карпат: автореф. дисс. на соискание науч. степени канд. биол. наук: спец. 03.00.05 “Ботаника” / Кобив Ю. И. – Днепропетровск, 1988. – 16 с.
 - 21 Слободян Г. М. Структура ценопопуляций послелесных черничников Черногоры: автореф. дисс. на соискание науч. степени канд. биол. наук: спец. 03.00.05 “Ботаника” / Слободян Г. М. – Днепропетровск, 1987. – 16 с.
 - 22 Сварнык Н. И. Структура популяций растений в сообществах сосны горной в Черногоре (Карпаты): автореф. дисс. на соискание науч. степени канд. биол. наук: спец. 03.00.05 “Ботаника” / Сварнык Н. И. – Днепропетровск, 1989. – 16 с.
 - 23 Вайнагий И. В. Семенная продуктивность и всхожесть семян некоторых высокогорных растений Карпат / И. В. Вайнагий // Бот. журн. – 1974. – Т. 59, № 10. – С. 1439–1451.
 - 24 Жиялев Г. Г. Жизнеспособность популяций растений / Г. Г. Жиялев. – Львов, 2005. – 304 с.
 - 25 Життєздатність популяцій рослин високогір'я Українських Карпат / [Царик Й. В., Жиялев Г. Г., Кияк В. Г. та ін.]; за ред. Й. В. Царика. – Львів: Меркатор, 2009. – 172 с.

Yu.Yu. Nesteruk, L.V. Hynda)^{26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31}. In particular, Volodymyr Kyiak studied small populations of rare species^{32, 33}.

Despite a significant number of publications and conducted research, rare species and plant communities of highland ecosystems of the Ukrainian Carpathians are still far from being studied in full. Until now, the intra- and inter-population diversity of many of them remains insufficiently studied. In particular, the genetic structure of populations, spatial distribution of individuals, the specifics of their reproduction, the impact of exogenous disturbances on the viability of populations, the characteristics of habitats, and their role in ensuring successful self-regeneration of populations remain poorly researched. Such information is necessary for clarifying the mechanisms that ensure the evolution of species, their adaptation to the changing environment, and the development of a systemic set of measures for their conservation, reproduction, and population monitoring under natural environment and anthropogenic conditions.

Altitude above sea level, exposure, and slope steepness significantly impact the development of mountain vegetation. Therefore, it is also advisable to consider mountain vegetation in the context of vertical zoning. In particular, the following vegetation zones are distinguished in the Ukrainian Carpathians: a belt of beech, fir-beech and beech-fir-spruce forests; a belt of spruce forests; subalpine and alpine belts³⁴. The two last form the vegetation of the highlands, the zonal character of which is clearly visible in all territories, with the exception of rocks, steep slopes, stone screes, and highland swamps.

The lower margin of the subalpine belt can pass at an altitude of 1200 m above sea level. The upper line reaches a height of 1800–1850 m. Shrub and meadow vegetation is common in the subalpine zone. Its lower boundary is mainly represented by mono- or bi-dominant communities of *Pinus mugo*, *Alnus viridis* (Chaix) DC., and common *Juniperus communis* subsp. *alpina* Čelak. The last plant formation usually occupies higher positions. Part of these phytocenoses

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- 26 Структура популяцій рідкісний видів флори Карпат / За ред. К. Малиновського. – Київ: Наук. думка, 1998. – 173 с.
 - 27 Стратегія популяцій рослин в природних і антропогеннозмінених екосистемах Карпат / За ред. М. Голубця, Й. Царика. – Львів: Євровіт, 2001. – 160 с.
 - 28 Рідкісні, ендемічні, реліктові та погранично-ареальні види рослин Українських Карпат / [Малиновський К. А., Царик Й. В., Кияк В. Г., Нестерук Ю. Й.]. – Львів: Ліґа-Прес, 2002. – 76 с.
 - 29 Внутрішньопопуляційна різноманітність рідкісних, ендемічних і реліктових видів рослин Українських Карпат / [Царик Й. В., Жилияєв Г. Г., Кияк В. Г. та ін.]; за ред. М. Голубця і К. Малиновського. – Львів: Поллі, 2004. – 198 с.
 - 30 Життєздатність популяцій рослин високогір'я Українських Карпат / [Царик Й. В., Жилияєв Г. Г., Кияк В. Г. та ін.]; за ред. Й. В. Царика. – Львів: Меркатор, 2009. – 172 с.
 - 31 Механізми самовідновлення популяцій: моногр. / [Білонога В. М., Гинда Л. В., Данилик І. М. та ін.]; за ред. Й. В. Царика. – Львів: Сполом, 2014. – 216 с.
 - 32 Кияк В. Г. Малі популяції рідкісних видів рослин високогір'я Українських Карпат: структура, стратегія, життєздатність: автореф. дис. на здобуття наук. ступеня докт. біол. наук: спец. 03.00.16 "Екологія" / Кияк В. Г. – Дніпропетровськ, 2009. – 38 с.
 - 33 Кияк В. Г. Репродуктивна ніша популяції / В. Г. Кияк // Біологічні студії. – 2013. – Том 7, № 3. – С. 233–246.
 - 34 Малиновський К. А. Рослинні угруповання високогір'я Українських Карпат / К. А. Малиновський, В. В. Крчфалушій. – Ужгород: Карпатська вежа, 2002. – 244 с.

was destroyed to expand the area of high mountain pastures. Secondary herbaceous phytocenoses are common for such territories, in which *Nardus stricta* and *Vaccinium myrtillus*³⁵ are prevailing.

The main phytocenoses of the subalpine zone are: *Nardetum*, *Festucetum rubrae*, *Festucetum supinae*, *Calamagrostidetum arundinaceae*, *Calamagrostidetum villosae*, *Deschampsietum caespitosae*, *Deschampsietum flexuosae*, less often – *Agrostidetum tenuisae*. Swamped areas are formed by *Carex* L., *Eriophorum* L., *Deschampsia caespitosa* (L.) Beauv., etc.³⁶

The alpine belt in the Ukrainian Carpathians occupies limited territories and is best represented in the Chornohora, Svydovets, and Maramures massifs. The alpine belt's lower line is at about 1800 m, and the upper line coincides with the peaks of the highest mountains (Hoverla – 2061 m). The alpine belt is characterized by the predominance of alpine meadows, shrubs, and open plant communities of rocks and stony outcrops, with a significant proportion of mosses and lichens³⁷. Highland phytocenoses include formations of *Salicetea herbaceae*, *Juncetea trifidi*, as well as various herbaceous formations of *Carici rupestris-Kobresietea belardii*, *Elyno-Seslerietea*, *Mulgedio-Aconitetea*, *Loiseleurio-Vaccinietae*. Cenoses with *Calamagrostis villosa* (Chaix) J.F. Gmel. are the most common among the secondary plant communities. Communities of *Luzula spadicea* (All.) DC. are characteristic of shaded and moist places. The stony outcrops and slopes with long-term snow and depleted substrate are characterized by communities of shrubs of the *Rhododendron kotschyi* Simk., *Salix herbacea* L., *Loiseleuria procumbens* (L.) Desv., and *Vaccinium uliginosum* L. The windward slopes are covered with lichens – *Cetraria islandica* (L.) Ach. and *Cladonia rangiferina* (L.) Weber ex F.H. Wigg.^{38, 39, 40}.

Rock plant communities are represented by species that are adapted to soils poor in nutrients, low air temperature, and intense solar radiation. Plants adapt to such specific conditions through a number of morphological, biological, and population mechanisms. Abundant pubescence of stems and leaves of *Antennaria dioica* (L.) Gaertn., *Hieracium alpinum* L., *Cerastium alpinum* L. subsp. *lanatum* (Lam.) Aschersonet Graebner, *Campanula alpina* Jacq., accelerated passage of ontogenesis stages, pillow-like and prostrate life forms of shrubs (*Empetrum nigrum* L. and *Loiseleuria procumbens*) – all this contributes to the successful functioning of organisms in the highlands. In rocky cenoses there are stenotopic groups with *Sesleria coeruleans*

35 Голубец М. А. Растительность / М. А. Голубец, Л. И. Милкина // Украинские Карпаты. Природа. – Киев: Наук. думка, 1988. – С. 51–63.

36 Чопик В. І. Високогірна флора Українських Карпат / В. І. Чопик. – К.: Наук. думка, 1976. – 270 с.

37 Життєздатність популяцій рослин високогір'я Українських Карпат / [Царик Й. В., Жилиєв Г. Г., Кияк В. Г. та ін.]; за ред. Й. В. Царика. – Львів: Меркатор, 2009. – 172 с.

38 Kricsfalusy V. Mountain grasslands of high conservation value in the Eastern Carpathians: syntaxonomy, biodiversity, protection and management / V. Kricsfalusy // Thaiszia. J. Bot., Košice. – 2013. – 23 (1). – P. 67–112.

39 Рідкісні, ендемічні, реліктові та погранично-ареальні види рослин Українських Карпат / [Малиновський К. А., Царик Й. В., Кияк В. Г., Нестерук Ю. Й.]. – Львів: Ліґа-Прес, 2002. – 76 с.

40 Життєздатність популяцій рослин високогір'я Українських Карпат / [Царик Й. В., Жилиєв Г. Г., Кияк В. Г. та ін.]; за ред. Й. В. Царика. – Львів: Меркатор, 2009. – 172 с.

Friv., *Festuca versicolor* Tausch, *F. amethystina* L., *Saxifraga paniculata* Mill., *Silene nutans* L. subsp. *dubia* (Herbich) Zapal., *Rhodiola rosea* L., *Anemone narcissiflora* L., *Bartsia alpina* L., etc.

The arctic-alpine element of the flora of Ukraine is mainly widespread in the Carpathian highlands⁴¹. In the Ukrainian Carpathians, the arctic-alpine element of the flora amounts to 67 species or about 7,4% of the flora of the highlands^{42, 43}. 55 species belong to the Holarctic area, 3 – to the Eurasian area, 6 – to the Euro-American area, and 3 – to the European area⁴⁴. The world areas of arctic-alpine species are disjunctive, which fact caused by fluctuations in the levels of continental glaciation, climate changes, and landscape development in the Holocene^{45, 46}.

In particular, the migration of species from the arctic regions to the areas of moderate latitudes took place during the glacial ages. 12 thousand years ago, the last ice age, which was characterized by a significant increase in the area of polar, continental and mountain glaciers, was over. The temperature decrease was so significant that the glaciers reached the regions of the Ukrainian Polissya. The mountain systems of Europe were also covered with a thick layer of ice. At that time, plant habitats were confined between ice-covered mountains and the southern edge of the continental glacier. After the last glaciation, another era of warming began, and it is still ongoing. This caused a change in natural conditions, to which cryophilous species had to adapt – post-glacial migration of plants began. On the one hand, plants began to climb the mountains; on the other – following the retreating glacier, cryophilous flora migrated to the north. Climate warming has affected the transformation of ecosystems and the reduction of the area of suitable habitats. Most of the arctic and alpine plants in the territory of the Great European Plain have died out. Arctic and sub-Arctic regions, as well as the mountain systems of the North Hemisphere – the Carpathians, the Alps, the Caucasus, etc., remained favourable ecotopes for the existence of cryophilous species. This geographical distance in the area of these species united them into one group – arctic-alpine organisms⁴⁷.

There is a significant part of rare species among arctic-alpine plants in the Ukrainian Carpathians. In particular, 28 species are listed in the Red Data Book of Ukraine⁴⁸. Of them, 16 are rare (R), 5 are

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- 41 Малиновський К. А. Рослинність високогір'я Українських Карпат / К. А. Малиновський. – К.: Наук. думка, 1980. – 280 с.
 - 42 Тасенкевич Л. Розмаїття флори судинних рослин в Українських Карпатах / Л. Тасенкевич // Праці Наук. товариства ім. Шевченка. Екологічний збірник. Екологічні проблеми Карпатського регіону. – Львів: НТШ, 2003. – Т. XII. – С. 147–157.
 - 43 Тасенкевич Л. О. Ареалогічна структура флори судинних рослин Карпат / Л. О. Тасенкевич // Наук. зап. Держ. природозн. музею. – 2005. – Вип. 21. – С. 11–28.
 - 44 Черепанин Р.М. Аркто-альпійські види рослин Українських Карпат. – Івано-Франківськ: Видавництво Прикарпатського національного університету імені Василя Стефаника, 2017. – 92 с.
 - 45 Сенчина Б. В. Еколого-географічні закономірності поширення популяцій аркто-альпійських видів рослин в Українських Карпатах: автореф. дис. на здобуття наук. ступеня канд. геогр. наук: спец. 11.00.05 "Біогеографія і географія ґрунтів" / Сенчина Б. В. – Львів, 2001. – 19 с.
 - 46 Сенчина Б. Сучасний стан та проблеми збереження аркто-альпійських видів рослин в Українських Карпатах / Б. Сенчина // Праці Наук. товариства ім. Шевченка. Екологічний збірник. Екологічні проблеми Карпатського регіону. – Львів: НТШ, 2003. – Т. XII. – С. 266–275.
 - 47 Черепанин Р.М. Аркто-альпійські види рослин Українських Карпат. – Івано-Франківськ: Видавництво Прикарпатського національного університету імені Василя Стефаника, 2017. – 92 с.
 - 48 Червона книга України. Рослинний світ / за ред. Я. П. Дідуха. – К.: Глобалконсалтинг, 2009. – 900 с.

vulnerable (VU), 5 are endangered (EN), 1 is not evaluated (NE), and 1 is extinct in the wild (EW). In particular: *Anemone narcissiflora* L. – VU, *Aster alpinus* L. – R, *Carex bicolor* Bellardi ex All. – R, *Carex fuliginosa* Schkuhr – R, *Carex pauciflora* Lightf. – VU, *Carex rupestris* All. – R, *Carex lachenalii* Schkuhr – EN, *Cerastium cerastoides* (L.) Britton – R, *Cystopteris montana* (Lam.) Bernh. ex Desv. – R, *Dryas octopetala* L. – R, *Gentiana nivalis* L. – EN, *Huperzia selago* (L.) Bernh. ex Schrank et Mart. – NE, *Pseudorchis albida* (L.) Á. & D. Löve – VU, *Lloydia serotina* (L.) Reichenb. – R, *Lycopodium alpinum* L. – R, *Loiseleuria procumbens* (L.) Desv. – R, *Minuartia verna* (L.) Hiern subsp. *gerardii* (Willk.) Hayek – R, *Oxyria digyna* (L.) Hill – R, *Pedicularis oederi* Vahl – EN, *Pinguicula alpina* L. – R, *Rhodiola rosea* L. – VU, *Salix herbacea* L. – R, *Saxifraga oppositifolia* L. – EW, *Saxifraga aizoides* L. – EN, *Saussurea alpina* (L.) DC. – R, *Selaginella selaginoides* (L.) P. Beauv. ex Schrank et C.F.P.Mart. – VU, *Veronica fruticans* Jacq. – R, *Woodsia alpina* (Bolton) S.F. Gray – EN. It is important to continue assessing the conservation status of species in accordance with international categories of rarity⁴⁹ and creating regional Red Lists^{50, 51, 52}.

Changes in the natural conditions and active development of highlands by humans often lead to the development of an unfavourable environment for rare plant species. A significant part of the primary plant communities of the Ukrainian Carpathians has undergone transformations. As a result of the destruction of the crooked forest of the subalpine zone, certain species and cenoses disappeared, anthropochores spread in the highlands, and secondary plant communities were formed⁵³. Today, as a result of climate warming, the introduction of the nature conservation status for certain territories and decay in mountain highland livestock farming, the next trends can be observed – raising of the upper forest limit, increasing the area of bushes, shrubs, small shrubs and dense grass communities in the highlands.

In order to effectively assess the state of populations of rare species, it is necessary to record the main structural and functional parameters in specific stationary areas. The following indicators should be used as the most informative criteria: population area, the total and effective number of individuals in the population, generative coefficient and recovery index, density of generative and vegetative individuals, and type of spatial arrangement of individuals.

When planning nature conservation measures, it is important to determine the critical conditions for the existence of populations. Information on the regenerative niche of species, which is often much narrower than the ecological niche of adult individuals, can be used for this. The possibility of the realization of a regenerative niche may become a determining factor

49 IUCN Red List Categories and Criteria: Version 3.1 Second edition. IUCN. – Gland, Switzerland and Cambridge, UK. – 2012. – 32 pp.

50 Карпатські сторінки Червоної книги України / За ред. В. Г. Собка. – Київ: Фітосоціоцентр, 2002. – 280 с.

51 Рідкісні, ендемічні, реліктові та погранично-ареальні види рослин Українських Карпат / [Малиновський К. А., Царик Й. В., Кияк В. Г., Нестерук Ю. Й.]. – Львів: Ліґа-Прес, 2002. – 76 с.

52 Нестерук Ю. Рослинний світ Українських Карпат. Чорногора. Екологічні мандрівки / Ю. Нестерук. – Львів: БАК, 2003. – 520 с.

53 Малиновський К. А. Рослинні угруповання високогір'я Українських Карпат / К. А. Малиновський, В. В. Крічфалушій. – Ужгород: Карпатська вежа, 2002. – 244 с.

for the existence of populations⁵⁴. While developing measures for the species' reintroduction, it is necessary to take into account information about their ecological and cenotic strategies and spatial variability of the regenerative niche because the ecological niche of generative individuals can be significantly different from the niche of the offspring. For example, favourable conditions for the regeneration of adult individuals can, at the same time, have a negative impact on the offspring's development and vice versa⁵⁵.

Protection of natural conditions for the habitats is important in the highlands of the Ukrainian Carpathians. Disruption of ecotopes and changes in habitat properties are the most threatening factors for many rare plant species. For example, the drying up of mesophytic meadows and highland bogs can cause a decrease in the volume of the only population of *Pedicularis oederi* in Ukraine and populations of *Carex pauciflora*. And the narrow ecological and cenotic amplitude of *Lloydia serotina* and the overgrowth of its ecotopes with *Pinus mugo*, as a result of the upper forest line's raising, causes a decrease in the number of individuals and a narrowed area of the already few habitats of this species. The overgrowth of the habitat with shrubs is also dangerous for the only population of *Saxifraga aizoides* in Ukraine in the Gadzhyna mountain area⁵⁶. Therefore, to conserve endangered plants, it is important to control demutation processes in unique ecosystems and, if necessary, to take active protection measures – to remove more competitive and aggressive species.

Also, it is important to comply with the appropriate nature protection regime within the nature conservation areas to conserve endangered species. For example, the population of the rare *Saussurea alpina* on Petros Mount (the Chornohora Range) is subjected to pastoral pressure. Grazing causes a decrease in the number and aging of the population, interruptions in the flowering of generative individuals, and a decrease in their vitality. A hiking trail passes through the *Saussurea* alpine population on Brebeneskul Mount. Considering the extraordinary value of the habitat, where there is the only population of *Callianthemum coriandrifolium* Reichenb. in Ukraine, as well as where rare *Rhodiola rosea* and *Ranunculus thora* L. grow, the recreational impact in this area should be significantly reduced. This can be achieved by arranging a tourist route through a roundabout path below the habitat.

Taking into account the low vitality of populations and the significant rarity of species, it is necessary to eliminate anthropogenic influence on them. First of all, this applies to grazing, trampling, plucking plants and collecting plant material⁵⁷.

However, removing land from economic use or absolute conservation does not always lead to the desired effect since the area of rare species' habitats decreases due to raising the upper

54 Wake D. B. Biogeography, changing climates, and niche evolution / D. B. Wake, E. A. Hadlyc, D. D. Ackerly // PNAS. – 2009. – Vol. 106. suppl. 2. – P. 19631–19636.

55 Кияк В. Г. Репродуктивна ніша популяції / В. Г. Кияк // Біологічні студії. – 2013. – Том 7, № 3. – С. 233–246.

56 Kobiv Y. *Saxifraga aizoides* (Saxifragaceae) in Ukraine / Y. Kobiv // Polish Botanical Journal. – 2016. – 61 (1). – P. 241–250.

57 Wojtuń B. Wartości przyrodnicze, zagrożenia i ochrona ekosystemów wysokogórskich Karkonoskiego Parku Narodowego / B. Wojtuń // Geoekologické problémy Krkonoš. Sborn. Mez. Věd. Konf., říjen 2006, Svoboda n. Úpou. Opera Corcontica, 44/1. – 2007. – S. 23–33.

forest limit and the overgrowth of meadows in some areas⁵⁸. Therefore, the implementation of active protection measures and regulated grazing in certain zones of nature conservation areas can contribute to the conservation of rare plant communities and the restoration of traditional forms of management.

Understanding the genetic structure of rare species is important for developing effective conservation measures. Such information is particularly valuable when we analyze small populations where gene drift is often observed, possibly leading to a significant decrease in genetic diversity⁵⁹. In addition, genetic research can answer questions about the mechanisms of genetic information exchange, evolutionary and geographic processes within a species, and the prospects for the existence of populations⁶⁰. Therefore, analysis of these processes requires future research.

Many rare species in highland ecosystems are protected in the territories of the Carpathian Biosphere Reserve, the Carpathian National Nature Park, and on the lands of other nature conservation institutions. For the successful conservation of rare species, it is necessary to continue working on expanding the conservation areas and creating new nature conservation objects. In particular, it would be relevant to grant conservation status to the mountain massifs Troyaska, Dohiaska, and Hereshaska in the northwestern part of the Svydovets Range⁶¹. Because a significant part of rare species is distributed in the Chornohora massif from Munchel Mount to Pip-Ivan Mount, it is also necessary to expand the nature conservation areas in the southeastern part of this massif. Chyvchyn Mount in the Chyvchyny Mountains, has the potential to create a botanical reserve there. In general, it is important to further monitor the rare species of highland ecosystems of the Ukrainian Carpathians to clarify their actual status and habitat conditions, create prognostic models of development and determine protection measures in different conditions of the natural environment and anthropogenic influence.

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- 61 Kagalo A., Kanarsky Y., Mykitchak T., Kovtoniuk O., et al. Nature conservation value of the central Svydovets Mountains (Ukrainian Carpathians) // Bulletin of the Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv. Geography 1 (70). 2018. – P. 35–48

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